

Point light sources based on pinhole InGaN/GaN microLED array for compact cell imaging systems

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For evolving applications in life sciences (e.g., cell counting and imaging), a compact system based on digital inline holographic microscopy provides a lightweight and cost-effective platform, which can be integrated in an incubator set-up enabling a real-time, in situ and continuous biological cell monitoring. Although commercial SMD-packaged LEDs can be employed, they still have limitations in terms of size, integration flexibility, spatial illumination coherency and achievable image resolution, especially when extension to 3D imaging and pixel super-resolution capabilities are required [1]. Combining SMD LEDs with optical fibers can offer a quick alternative solution for realizing an array of small, separately controllable light emitters. However, the efficient interconnection between those two elements, as well as device miniaturization still remain a challenge. Therefore, smaller point light sources forming arrays, which can be specifically designed and fully integrated into a miniaturized imaging system, would offer tremendous advantages.

In this work, pinhole-shaped microLED arrays with openings ranging from 100 μm down to 5 μm have been designed and fabricated from planar GaN LED wafer. To start the fabrication of the device, an insulating SiO_2 layer is deposited on the p -GaN surface of InGaN/GaN LED wafer, which is followed by sequential photolithography and etching processes to realize openings of the holes (for transparent p -contact) and larger n -contact areas (Figure 1). Different thin metal layers, such as Ti/Au and Pd/Au, are deposited and subsequently annealed to produce the contacts. Finally, metallization defines both electric connection of the LEDs and the dimension of the pinhole LEDs (Figure 2(a)). Prior to integration into lensless holographic microscope, the LED device is characterized in an electroluminescence (EL) measurement at room temperature. The experimental I-V curves (Figure 2(b)) indicate that the LED device can operate under normal bias voltages of around 3 V. For testing its capability as an enhanced point light source, a single 90 μm pinhole LED is assembled into the lensless holographic microscope to image polystyrene microbeads with diameters of 5 μm , which is comparable to the size of most cell nuclei [2]. From the captured images, we observed that the interference and diffraction effect from the dense microbead clusters can be reduced by using the produced pinhole LED. This resulted in images with better resolution than those obtained by commercial blue SMD LED (Figure 3).

[1] A.C. Sobieranski, F. Inci, H.C. Tekin, M. Yuksekkaya, E. Comunello, D. Cobra, A. von Wangenheim, U. Demirci. *Light: Science & Applications* 4 (2015), e346.

[2] L.T. Threadgold, *The ultrastructure of the animal cell: international series in pure and applied biology*, (2nd edition, Netherlands, Amsterdam, 2017).

Figure 1. Fabrication process of pinhole LEDs, consisting of (a) Preparation and cleaning of GaN LED wafers, (b) deposition of SiO_2 as insulating layer, (c) opening of holes and contacts on SiO_2 layer, (d) dry etching down to n -GaN, (e) deposition of Ti/Au as n -contact, (f) deposition of thin and transparent Pd/Au as p -contact, and (g) metallization using Cr/Au, subsequently defining pinhole openings, which emit blue light after contacting.

Figure 2. (a) 3D schematic of the pinhole LED array. (b) Measured I-V curve of a single pinhole LED having a diameter of 90 μm .

Figure 3. Side-by-side comparison of the reconstructed images of 5 μm microbeads embedded in transparent polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) using illuminations of (a) a commercial blue SMD LED with a size of $230 \times 230 \mu\text{m}^2$ and (b) a single pinhole LED with diameter of 90 μm both at a wavelength of 465 nm. In contrast to (a), clear diffraction patterns can be seen in (b) due to the larger spatial coherence length of the microLEDs.